

OPTIMIZATION OF THE FORMULATION FOR THE PRODUCTION OF ENRICHED BREAKFAST MEAL FROM WHOLE-WHEAT, ACHA AND ELM OYSTER MUSHROOM (*Hypsizygus ulmarius*) FLOUR BLENDS

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ABSTRACT

The research optimized the formulation for the production of an enriched breakfast meal from blends of whole wheat, acha and Elm oyster mushroom flours. The wheat and acha grains procured from Shasha Market, Osogbo and Jos respectively were sorted, wet cleaned, dried, milled, sieved and packaged separately inside airtight plastic containers at room temperature. Elm oyster mushroom clusters purchased from LTC mushroom farm Osogbo were cleaned to remove extraneous materials, sliced, soaked in 0.5% salt solution for 5 minutes, drained, dried, milled, sieved and packaged into airtight containers. Sixteen runs of blends from three mixture components set at 0-100% wheat, 0-100% acha and 0-15% mushroom flours were designed using I-optimal mixture design of Design Expert 13 software package for the production of breakfast meal and the optimum formulation blend was confirmed by desirability plots. The blends were drum-dried at 150 °C, drum speed of 5 rpm and feed concentration of 30%. The optimum formulation was established using selected responses such as protein, fibre, peak viscosity (PV), water absorption capacity (WAC), swelling capacity (SWC), α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory activities (AAIA and AGIA), 1, 1-diphenylpicrylhydrazine (DPPH) radical scavenging activity, total phenolic content (TPC), Carr index (CI), calcium and potassium contents of the samples. The results showed that the actual optimum blend was experimental run 3 of the mixture constituents: 65.63%, 23.13% and 11.25% correlated with the desirability plots of 67.9%, 22.4% and 9.8% for wheat, acha and mushroom, respectively. The increased addition of mushroom had significant effect ($p \leq 0.05$) on the protein, DPPH, TPC, AGIA and AAIA of the samples. The results of the predicted responses of the optimum blend were 17.75%, 1.04%, 7.53 mg/100g, 8.02 mg/100g, 626.75%, 483.58%, 42.97, 891.78 RVU, 0.46 mgGAE/mg, 54.74%, 31.36% and 48.07% for protein, fibre, calcium, potassium, SWC, WAC, CI, PV, TPC, DPPH, AGIA and AAIA, respectively. The model terms for protein, SWC, WAC, Carr index, TPC and AGIA were significant at $p \leq 0.05$. The study established the optimum blend formulation for the production of an enriched drum-dried breakfast meal.

Keywords: Breakfast meal, Drum drying, Product formulation, Mushroom, Optimization

INTRODUCTION

Breakfast cereals are those meals that are mostly produced from grains and are regarded as a main morning meal when served with either hot or cold milk. They are consumed globally and are broadly grouped into instant/ready-to-eat (RTE) cereals and hot/traditional cereals (Fast, 2000). There is need for extra preparation before hot cereals can be consumed, while the RTE cereals are instant and ready for consumption with little or no preparation required (Kapoor *et al.*, 2020; Akonor *et al.*, 2021). They are sometimes made from blends of different grains such as wheat, sorghum, maize, rice, acha, or millet and legumes and oilseeds are also added with other ingredients such as flavourings, dried fruits, sweeteners, etc. (Asma *et al.*, 2006; Eshun *et al.*,

2011, Emelike *et al.*, 2020). Wheat is deemed as an important energy source in a complex carbohydrate form, that is found in the starchy endosperm that contributes to 80% of the grain. It also has substantial quantities of other macronutrients such as proteins, fiber and small components of lipids and other micronutrients that may have beneficial impact on the wellbeing of man such as vitamins (B-group and E), minerals (Fe, Zn, Mg, Cu, and P), bioactive compounds (phenolic acids, flavonoids, carotenoids etc.) and phytochemicals (Shewry and Hey, 2015; Khalid *et al.*, 2023). However, in the making of most wheat-based products, the use of refined flour is quite popular. The refining process has been associated with the loss of nutrients and health relevant components due to the removal of the bran and germ from the flour (Zhu and Sang, 2017; Jones and Poutanen, 2020). Also, most of the

products made from refined wheat flour have been recognized to have high glycemic index (Kumar and Prabhasankar, 2014).

Acha has been reported to have become increasingly popular worldwide due to its nutritional benefits and its fast-cultivation rate (The European Commission, 2009; Zhu, 2020). It is rich in methionine and cysteine, when compared to other grains and legumes, which are important to the health of humans (Sarwar, 2013). It has also been reported to have other attractive range and quality of health benefiting bioactive compounds that are largely comparable with other cereals (Stuper-Szablewska and Perkowski, 2019). However, it still remains a grossly underutilized and neglected grain in Nigeria (Inyang *et al.*, 2018). Also, its overall protein content is low and it is lacking in lysine (same with wheat and many other grains) which is a very important essential amino acid.

Hypsizygus ulmarius, also known as *Pleurotus ulmarius* or Elm oyster mushroom, is a member of the order of *Agaricales*; *Tricholomataceae* family (Jatav *et al.*, 2012). It has a fleshy and large fruiting body that is made up of the cap that has furrow like gills underneath and stipe which is the central stalk. It is a high yielding specie with a remarkable meaty flavor and excellent taste (Shivashankar and Premkumari, 2014; Sumi and Geetha 2016). It has been reported to have great nutritional quality with high protein (at 23% or more), high fibre (at 9% or more), rich antioxidants and antidiabetic contents. Also, *H. ulmarius* may be deemed as a valuable source of phytochemicals that can be exploited as food additives and in pharmaceuticals (Sethi *et al.*, 2012; Shivashankar and Premkumari, 2014; Usha and Suguna, 2015; Panavalappil *et al.*, 2016).

Drum-drying is a common, simple and economical food processing method that is used for the production of nutritionally, texturally and functionally acceptable instant cereals (otherwise known as RTE cereals) (Akonor *et al.*, 2021). It is a short time and high temperature indirect contact drying technique that involves the use of hydrothermal processing method to dry thick liquids, pulps and slurries mostly from cereals and legumes into thin sheets which can be further processed into powders or flakes (Valous *et al.*, 2002; Tang *et al.*, 2003; Kakade *et al.*, 2011; Almena *et al.*, 2019). In addition, drum-dried food products can be reconstituted without stress into an easy to eat instant porridge of soft consistency and thus, frequently used in breakfast meals (Bonazzi *et al.*, 1996; Akonor *et al.*, 2021).

The optimization of food production process is necessary to achieve product development, maintain product quality and process efficiency (Pornthip and Maradee, 2018). It helps to manipulate many variables of fewer experimental runs in order to improve the performance of food system (Garayo and Moreira 2002; Quoe *et al.*, 2012). Optimization can be achieved by Response Surface Methodology (RSM), which is a statistical and mathematical system of deriving model equations that determine specific response whose result is affected by many variables and define the interactions

between these variables (Akonor *et al.*, 2021). Mixture design is a very practical optimization method for choosing the best combination of ingredients in a blend (Ogundele *et al.*, 2016). Different studies have engaged optimal mixture design of RSM for the optimization and statistical analysis of nutritional characteristics of composite flour from different food materials blends (Omoba *et al.*, 2013; Awolu *et al.*, 2016; Bamigbala *et al.*, 2016).

The paradigm shifts from the traditional to modern lifestyle in recent years has piqued the interest of consumers as regards packed ready to eat foods (Vijayeta, 2015). There has been a significant increase in the advocacy and demand for delicious, whole-grain and high-quality instant meals (Jebaraj, 2014; Whole Grain Initiative, 2020). This can be associated with the increased awareness on the importance of functional ingredients in foods in the prevention and management of underlying diseases, such as type-2-diabetes, that might accompany the currently adopted fast-paced lifestyle (Inbalakshmi *et al.*, 2014). Mushrooms are good source of protein, vitamins and minerals (Khan *et al.*, 2008) and are known to have a broad range of uses both as food and medicine (Alice and Kustudia, 2004). Due to their high nutritional values especially when comparing the rich level of the amino acid to those from animal and plant sources, food industries and science community are recently becoming drawn to proteins of fungal (Bach *et al.*, 2017). Hence, the study seeks to optimize the formulation for the production of an enriched breakfast meal from whole-wheat, acha and Elm oyster mushroom flours.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fresh clusters of the fruiting body of *Hypsizygus ulmarius* were obtained from a mushroom farm at Ofatedo, Osogbo, Osun State. Wheat grains were procured from a local market in Osogbo while acha grains were bought from a local market in Jos, Plateau State.

Sample preparation

The whole wheat and acha flour were processed into flour using the method described by Olapade and Aworh, (2012) as shown in Figures 1 and 2. The mushroom flour was produced by modifying the method described by Mutukwa *et al.*, (2019) in Figure 3. The method described by Akonor *et al.*, (2021) was used for the breakfast sample production with some modifications as shown in Figure 4.

Experimental Design for the Formulation for Breakfast Meal Production and Optimization

The blends for the production of the breakfast meal samples were formulated using I-Optimal Mixture Design of Design Expert 13 package as shown in Table 1. Sixteen combinations were generated in random order. A three-factor experimental set up was used with three mixture components (wheat - A, acha -B and mushroom - C flours). The factor ranges for the wheat, acha and mushroom flours were 0-100%, 0-100% and 0-15% respectively as seen in Table 2, while the responses used for

the optimization were protein, fibre, calcium, potassium, swelling capacity, water absorption capacity, Carr index, total phenolic content (TPC), DPPH radical scavenging

activity (DPPH), α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory activities (AAIA and AGIA). Optimization of the responses was carried out through desirability approach.

Figure 1: Flowchart for the Production of Acha Flour

Figure 2: Flowchart for the Production of Whole Wheat Flour

Figure 3: Flowchart for the Production of Elm Oyster Mushroom Flour

Figure 4: Flowchart for the Production of Drum Dried Breakfast Meal (Modified Methods Akonor et al., 2021)

Table 1: Mixture Components for the Formulation of Breakfast Meal from Whole-wheat, Acha and Mushroom Flours

Component	Name	Unit	Type	Minimum	Maximum	Coded low	Coded high	Mean	Std. Dev.
A	Wheat	%	Mixture	0	100	+0 ↔ 0	+1 ↔ 100	45.677	32.436
B	Acha	%	Mixture	0	95	+0 ↔ 0	+1 ↔ 100	47.370	31.782
C	Mushroom	%	Mixture	0	15	+0 ↔ 0	+0.15 ↔ 15	6.953	5.933
Total =				100		L_Pseudo Coding			

Table 2: Experimental Runs for the Optimization of the Product Formulation from Whole-wheat, Acha and Mushroom Flour Blends

Run	Whole wheat (%)	Acha (%)	Mushroom (%)
1	0	95	5
2	100	0	0
3	65.63	23.13	11.25
4	85	0	15
5	46.25	46.25	7.5
6	33.33	66.67	0
7	100	0	0
8	46.25	46.25	7.5
9	56.67	28.33	15
10	66.67	33.33	0
11	28.33	56.67	15
12	46.25	46.25	7.5
13	0	95	5
14	33.33	66.67	0
15	23.13	69.37	7.5
16	0	85	15

Sample Analyses

The samples were analyzed for protein and fibre content, mineral composition (calcium and potassium), pasting property (pasting viscosity), functional properties (water absorption and swelling capacities), 1, 1-Diphenylpicrylhydrazine (DPPH) radical scavenging activity, total phenolic content (TPC), α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory activities (AAIA and AGIA).

i. Determination of Protein and Fibre Contents

The protein and crude fibre contents of the samples were analyzed using AOAC (2005) methods.

ii. Determination of the mineral composition

The calcium and potassium contents of the samples were evaluated using AOAC (2005) method.

iii. Pasting Properties

Pasting characteristics was determined by a Rapid Visco Analyzer (Tecmaster S/N2122833-TMB, Australia) using the method described by Ayo *et al.* (2018).

iv. Functional Properties

Water absorption capacity of the drum-dried breakfast meal samples (BFMS) was analyzed using the method described

by Onwuka (2005). Swelling capacity of the BFMS was analyzed using a modified technique of Sathe and Salunke (1981) at 80 °C.

v. 1, 1-Diphenylpicrylhydrazine (DPPH) radical scavenging activity

The samples were evaluated for DPPH radical scavenging activities using the stable radical process described by Pownall *et al.* (2010).

vi. Total phenolic content (TPC)

The TPC of each sample was evaluated using the Folin-Ciocalteu method (Singleton *et al.*, 1997) with some adjustments.

vii. α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory activities (AAIA and AGIA)

Inhibition of porcine α -amylase activity present in the samples was carried out through the dinitrosalicylic acid technique described by Kwon *et al.* (2006) while the method described by Kim *et al.* (2005) was used to evaluate the α -glucosidase inhibitory activity of the samples.

Statistical analysis

The optimization of the product formulation was carried out by adopting Optimal Mixture Design of Design Expert 13 package to generate sixteen runs of experiments.

responses for the optimization are shown in Table 4 and discussed as follow:

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Formulation on Selected Properties of Breakfast Meal from Whole-wheat, Acha and Mushroom Flour Blends

Table 3 shows the results of the mixture components and the responses that were used for the optimization of the formulation of breakfast meal from whole-wheat, acha and mushroom. The results of the analysis of variance of the

i. Protein and Fibre Contents of Breakfast Meal Formulation

The breakfast meal sample (BFMS) from run 4 had the highest protein content of 20.79% with the blending ratio of 85:0:15 of whole wheat, acha and mushroom flours, respectively as shown in Table 3, while run 3 was found to be most preferred. The protein content of the samples was observed to increase with the addition of mushroom and decrease with increase in acha ratio as shown in Figure 5.

Table 3: Mixture Components and Responses for Optimization of the Formulation of Breakfast Meal

Run	Components			Responses											
	A:Wheat	B:Acha	C:Mushroom	Protein (%)	Fibre (%)	Ca (mg/100g)	K (mg/100g)	SWC (%)	WAC (%)	Carr index	Peak viscosity (RVU)	TPC (mgGAE/g)	DPPH (%)	AGIA (%)	AAIA (%)
1	0.00	95.00	5.00	14.08	0.84	7.30	7.35	541.13	562.11	23.74	816.50	0.44	36.63	31.68	46.27
2	100.00	0.00	0.00	14.82	0.96	6.00	8.30	671.89	528.49	23.62	1164.50	0.45	46.42	32.76	48.24
3	65.63	23.13	11.25	15.16	0.96	8.00	7.50	641.49	446.47	45.12	946.00	0.37	54.62	32.20	53.01
4	85.00	0.00	15.00	20.79	0.90	8.30	8.00	637.50	438.55	44.05	775.00	0.35	51.31	31.34	43.85
5	46.25	46.25	7.50	20.27	1.12	6.20	7.20	631.13	464.34	27.38	1108.50	0.45	43.86	30.57	39.27
6	33.33	66.67	0.00	10.79	0.85	7.00	7.80	624.10	520.09	29.55	1495.50	0.25	49.73	21.94	38.89
7	100.00	0.00	0.00	14.66	0.95	8.30	8.40	604.41	493.93	23.80	1178.00	0.45	46.07	32.47	48.06
8	46.25	46.25	7.50	20.15	1.12	8.40	7.10	615.56	456.58	25.00	904.00	0.46	43.73	30.33	39.59
9	56.67	28.33	15.00	16.32	0.96	7.20	8.40	613.44	433.50	48.28	498.00	0.38	49.66	36.04	55.41
10	66.67	33.33	0.00	15.00	1.07	7.10	8.80	674.52	548.79	27.73	1464.00	0.39	39.66	17.11	38.95
11	28.33	56.67	15.00	20.13	0.85	7.00	8.00	573.86	552.43	22.88	538.50	0.30	47.17	30.81	45.66
12	46.25	46.25	7.50	18.16	0.91	7.70	9.40	609.69	593.20	28.86	900.00	0.35	51.87	34.01	53.60
13	0.00	95.00	5.00	18.82	0.85	8.80	10.90	539.83	569.72	14.64	830.50	0.43	35.59	31.61	46.03
14	33.33	66.67	0.00	10.73	0.86	8.30	11.80	645.01	587.31	17.23	1493.00	0.26	49.38	21.59	38.65
15	23.13	69.38	7.50	15.66	0.96	7.50	7.70	565.50	579.53	14.77	791.00	0.24	45.11	30.81	51.31
16	0.00	85.00	15.00	19.34	0.93	8.50	8.50	542.69	544.00	27.85	446.50	0.24	53.45	34.33	54.82

Key: Ca: Calcium; K: Potassium; SWC: Swelling capacity; WAC: Water absorption capacity; TPC: Total phenolic content; DPPH: 1, 1-diphenylpicrylhydrazine radical scavenging activity; AALA and AGIA: α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory activities.

Table 4: Analysis of Variance Table for Mixture Regression Models of the Responses

Response	Model	F-value	p-value	R ²	Predicted R ²	Adjusted R ²	Adequate precision	Lack of fit	Significance of Model
Protein	Linear	5.98	0.0144	0.4792	0.2654	0.3990	5.613	3.04	Significant
Fibre	Special Cubic	2.54	0.1013	0.6284	0.0515	0.3806	4.4737	0.6345	Not significant
Calcium	Linear	0.5612	0.5837	0.0795	-0.4950	-0.0621	2.3004	0.2031	Not significant
Potassium	Linear	1.18	0.3377	0.1538	-0.2456	0.0237	3.0379	0.1276	Not significant
SWC	Quadratic	11.35	0.0007	0.8502	0.4939	0.7754	10.4651	0.5907	Significant
WAC	Linear	6.79	0.0096	0.5107	0.3525	0.4355	7.5833	0.3662	Significant
Carr Index	Special quartic	9.71	0.0036	0.9174	0.1521	0.8229	10.3019	0.0223	Significant
Peak viscosity	Special Cubic	33.53	<0.0001	0.9572	0.8898	0.9286	17.9529	1.92	Significant
TPC	Cubic	7.74	0.0180	0.9207	-0.4640	0.8016	7.2066	0.5645	Significant
DPPH	Cubic	4.04	0.0518	0.8582	-7.1438	0.6456	7.0791	2.64	Not significant
AAIA	Special quartic	32.41	<0.0001	0.9737	0.4720	0.9437	20.0478	0.5751	Significant
AGIA	Linear	2.33	0.1363	0.2640	-0.1280	0.1508	3.5852	1.28	Not significant

SWC: Swelling capacity; WAC: Water absorption capacity; TPC: Total phenolic content; DPPH: 1, 1-diphenylpicrylhydrazine radical scavenging activity; AALA and AGIA: α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory activities

Edible mushroom is believed to contain all the essential amino acids necessary in human diet (Kumar, 2015). It is believed that protein deficiency that is prevalent in developing countries can be alleviated using edible mushrooms (Kumar, 2020). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to evaluate how the formulation of flour blends affected the protein content of the drum-dried breakfast meal samples as shown in Table 4. The model was linear as shown in Equation 1 and at a p-value less than 0.05 indicated that the model terms for protein was significant. It was observed that the F-value of the model was 5.98 which also implied that the model was significant. Also, the predicted R² value (0.2654), although low, was in agreement with the adjusted R² value (0.3990) and the model had an adequate precision of 5.6513 which is greater than 4, thus, confirming that the model is accurate. The coefficient of determination (R²) was given as 0.4792 which means that about 47.92% of variability in the response can be explained by the model.

BFMS produced from the blend of the mixture components of Run 5 had the highest fibre content (1.12%) (see Table 3). Figure 6 shows that the fibre content of the samples increased with increasing addition of mushroom and wheat. This may be associated with the whole wheat flour used in the formulation of these samples. According to Oliveira *et al.* (2015), the addition of whole grain wheat flour was

$$\text{Protein} = 14.283A + 13.536B + 52.016C \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Fibre} = 0.960 A + 0.596B + -17.697 C + 0.746AB + 21.564AC + 24.058BC + -6.054ABC \quad (2)$$

ii. Calcium and Potassium Composition of Breakfast Meal Formulation

Run 13 ratio of flour blends (66.67:33.33:0 of whole wheat: acha: mushroom flours) gave the BFMS with the highest calcium content (8.80 mg/100g), but the most preferred was found to be run 3 having calcium content of 8.00 mg/100g. Figure 7 showed that the calcium content increased significantly with the addition of acha while the absence of wheat did not significantly reduce the calcium of the BFMS. Calcium in diet is vital for the maintenance of the general wellbeing of the body and it also ensures that the nerves and the muscles function properly (Piste *et al.*, 2013). The model obtained for Calcium is as shown in Equation 3. The linear model obtained had a large F-value (0.5837) which could have occurred due to noise and implied that the model is not significant. The p-value (0.2031) was also higher than 0.005. The negative predicted R² value is implying that the overall mean of the response may be a better predictor than the current model. BFMS from Run 14 had the highest potassium content (11.8 mg/100g). The value was lower than 0.22 -0.27 mg/g

Figure 5: Contour Plot of Protein Contents of the Samples as Affected by the Blending Ratios

Figure 6: Contour plot of Fibre Contents of the Samples as Affected by the Blending Ratios

found to have had a positive effect on the fibre content of an extruded breakfast cereal. The model suggested for fibre was special cubic as shown in Equation 2 and at a F-value of 2.54 and p-value of 0.1013 which is higher than 0.05 and this implied that the model for fibre was not significant. The predicted R² (0.0515) and adjusted R² (0.3806) values had a difference that was more than 0.2 indicating a large block effect and the adequate precision (4.4737) was higher than 4 showing that the model though not significant can still be used to navigate through the design.

reported by Ayo *et al.* (2018) for the biscuit produced from acha-mushroom blend. As shown in Figure 8, the potassium content was not significantly influenced by the addition of mushroom but was positively affected by the addition of acha. Potassium is important for amino acid and protein synthesis in the body (Ayo *et al.*, 2018). Linear model was also obtained for Potassium as shown in Equation 4. The F-value of 1.18 is indicating that the model was not significant in comparison to noise and at p-value (0.3377) greater than 0.05, confirms that the model

was not significant. The adequate precision of 7.5833 indicated an adequate signal for the model to relevant in the design space.

$$\text{Calcium} = 7.162A + 7.720B + 9.664C \quad (3)$$

Figure 7: Contour Plot of Calcium Contents of the Samples as Affected by the Blending Ratios

$$\text{Potassium} = 495.605A + 602.196B + 119.411C \quad (4)$$

iii. Swelling Capacity, Water Absorption Capacity, Carr Index and Peak Viscosity of Breakfast Meal Formulation

The swelling capacity of the samples were favorably affected by addition of the grain flours, especially the wheat flour. BFMS from Run 10 exhibited the highest SWC (674.52%) as shown in Table 3 but run 3 was found to be must preferred of SWC of 641.49%. The values were high but

Figure 9: Contour Plot of Swelling Capacities of the Samples as Affected by the Blending Ratios

not as high as the results of drum dried instant rice cereal with soybean and tigernut at 945 to 1143% (Annan *et al.*, 2023). The result of the SWC showed the interactions of the intermolecular starch polymers and the presence of components that were high in starch will always have direct

Figure 8: Contour Plot of Potassium Contents of the Samples as Affected by the Blending Ratios

effect on SWC (Tortoe *et al.*, 2019). The quadratic model result for swelling capacity (SW) was shown in Equation 5 with a p-value of 0.007 and a large F-value of 11.35 indicated high statistical significance of swelling capacity on the blend formulation. The R² of 0.8502 suggests that the model could explained 85.02% of the data and adequate precision of 10.4651 showed the model had adequate signal to navigate the design space.

As shown in Table 3, BFMS from Run 12 had the highest water absorption capacity. WAC was significantly affected

Figure 10: Contour Plot of Water Absorption Capacities of the Samples as Affected by the Blending Ratios

by the presence of wheat and acha flour as shown in Figure 10. The viscosity profile of the samples may be altered due to the fibre present in whole wheat flour (Oliveira *et al.*, 2015). The presence of hydrophilic starch granules enables water absorption and can be related to high gelatinization level (Kaur and Singh, 2005). Acha has been reported to have high water absorption which has been linked to its significant pentosan quantity (Ayo and Kajo, 2016). For water absorption capacity, a linear model as shown in Equation (6) was obtained for the response. The predicted R^2 (0.3525) was in good agreement with the adjusted R^2 value (0.4355) and the adequate precision value of 7.5833 showed that WAC was relevant to the formulation of the sample blends. The ANOVA evaluation of Carr Index gave a special quartic model as shown in Equation (7). The model was significant, the R^2 value was high suggested that the model was a good fit and the adequate precision of

$$WAC = 495.605A + 602.196B + 119.411C \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Carr Index} = 23.7551A + 11.6847B + -211.162C + 35.089AB + 434.879AC + 389.298BC + 511.241A^2BC + -2,459.73 AB^2C + 3,845.81ABC^2 \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Peak viscosity} = 1,171.08A + 1,043.44B + 393.154C + 1,703.58AB + -2,068.48AC + -3,969.81BC + -14,505.8ABC \quad (8)$$

iv. DPPH, TPC and Anti-Diabetic Activities of Breakfast Meal Formulation

The highest DPPH radical scavenging activity occurred in BFMS from one of the blends with the highest ratio of mushroom, that is, run 3 as shown in Table 3. Thus, it can be said that the increased addition mushroom had significant ($p \leq 0.05$) influence on this response (Figure 13).

Figure 11: Contour Plot of Carr Index of the Samples as Affected by the Blending Ratios

Figure 12: Contour Plot of Peak Viscosities of the Samples as Affected by the Blending Ratios

10.302 also showed that the Carr index was significant to the formulation design of the breakfast meal samples.

Peak viscosity was highest in BFMS from Run 6 (1495.5 RVU) while BFMS from Run 16 had the lowest (446.6 RVU). The peak viscosities of the breakfast meal sample were positively affected by the presence of the grains, especially acha as seen in Table 3 and Figure 12. Annan *et al.* (2023) reported that increasing portion of starch-based components in the formulation encouraged the paste formation and thickening of drum dried product made from rice, tigernut and soyabean. The peak viscosity displayed a significant special cubic model as seen in Equation (8) with p -value of <0.0001 and F -value 33.53. The predicted R^2 and adjusted R^2 were in agreement and adequate precision was quite high and indicated that the model was of good fit. The lack of fit of all the responses were not significant and this indicated model fitness.

$$SW = 644.328A + 571.076B + 2,713.31C + 176.977AB + -2,523.19AC + -2,878.47BC \quad (5)$$

Edible mushroom has been reported to have successfully reduce lipid oxidation when used as synthetic antioxidant alternative (Reis *et al.*, 2012; Adebayo *et al.*, 2018). Mushroom has also been said to produce bioactive compounds which serve a lot of health benefitting purposes such as antioxidant, antimicrobial, immune-modulating. The ANOVA analysis for DPPH obtained a cubic model (Equation 9) that was not significant with p -value 0.0518 and the F -value was 4.04 meaning this large F -value is 5.18% likely to be caused by noise. The lack of fit was not significant, and the adequate precision value was 7.0791, meaning the response is still relevant to the formulation design regardless of its insignificant model.

The contour plot for total phenolic contents (Figure 14) showed that the maximum content was present in the drumdried sample produced from Run 8 that had equal blends of wheat and acha with 7.5% mushroom flour. As reported by Sihdu *et al.*, (2017), the outer bran layers of wheat grain are rich in phenolic compounds like ferulic, caffeic, chlorogenic, p -coumaric and so on, which have been

identified to have anticarcinogenic and antioxidant health benefits. Also, the presence of significant phenolic contents may indicate immune enhancing, antioxidant and hormone modulating activities of the product (Okwu and Omodamiro, 2005). The TPC also had a cubic model after ANOVA analysis as presented in Equation 10. The model had p-value that was lower than 0.05 and F-value of 7.74 which implied that the model was significant to the formulation design for the breakfast meal production. The R² was high at 0.9207 and the adequate precision was greater than 4 and this showed that the model had adequate signal and is fit for the design.

and Figures 15 and 16). Generally, mushroom is an excellent source of anti-diabetic bioactive compounds that have been found very effective for the control of blood sugar and diabetes related issues (Kumar *et al.*, 2021). The ANOVA analysis for AGIA and AAIA gave special quartic and quadratic models respectively as shown in Equations 11 and 12. The model for AGIA was significant and this was confirmed with a p-value <0.0001 of and F-value at 32.41 implying there was less the 0.01% chance that the F-value occurred due to noise. Also, the R² value of AGIA was very close to 1 and had an adequate precision of 20.0478. This implied the model is reliable for predicting the AGIA of

Figure 13: Contour Plot of DPPH Radical Scavenging Activities of the Samples as Affected by the Blending Ratios

Figure 14: Contour Plot of Total Phenolic Contents of the Samples as Affected by the Blending Ratios

Figure 15: Contour Plot of AGIA of the Samples as Affected by the Blending Ratios

Figure 16: Contour Plot of AAIA of the Samples as Affected by the Blending Ratios

For the antidiabetic properties, BFMS from Run 9 had the highest AGIA and AAIA. It can be deduced that high mushroom ratio (15%) had a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) positive effect on the antidiabetic properties of the sample (Table 3

the breakfast meal samples. The model for AAIA was not significant. However, the adequate precision of 5.0107 suggested that AAIA may still be relevant to the

formulation design even though the model was not significant.

$$DPPH = 46.013A + 54.455B + -23,485.5C + -23.6013AB + 37,202.5AC + 39,145.5BC + -29,909.1ABC + -37.0093AB (A-B) + -13,530.2AC(A-C) + -16,382.2BC(B-C) \quad (9)$$

$$TPC = 0.450A + 0.483B + 938.908C + -0.675AB + -1,542.92AC + -1,515.32BC + 1,217.07ABC + 0.903859AB(A-B) + 625.703AC(A-C) + 584.855BC(B-C) \quad (10)$$

$$AAIA = 47.393A + 38.251B + -280.114C + -14.353AB + 392.905AC + 503.461BC \quad (11)$$

$$AGIA = 32.604A + 47.5656B + 1,901.86C + -93.111AB + -2,208.84AC + -2,285.52BC + 3,198.49A2BC + 2,469.46AB2 C + -11,780.8ABC2 \quad (12)$$

Optimization and validation of optimal breakfast meal formulation

The numerical optimization of the formulation was concluded by desirability and the optimum desirability was 80.8% with ratio of wheat, acha and mushroom flours at 67.9:22.4:9.7, respectively as shown in Figures 17 and 18. The results of predicted responses were 17.75%, 1.04%, 7.53 mg/100g, 8.02 mg/100g, 626.75%, 483.58%, 42.97, 891.78 RVU, 0.46 mgGAE/mg, 54.74%, 31.36% and 48.07% for protein, fibre, calcium, potassium, SWC, WAC, CI, PV, TPC, DPPH, AGIA and AAIA, respectively. Comparing these results with those of the 16 experimental runs earlier designed, the predicted blend was most similar to the designed flour blend in run 3 (65.63% wheat, 23.13% acha and 11.3% mushroom flours) as shown in Table 5. Except for protein and TPC, the percentage deviation between the two results were minimal, meaning the results were in good agreement with each other. In fact, for responses such as calcium, SWC, CI, PV, AGIA and AAIA, the results of the experimental run 3 were better than those of the predicted run.

Figure 17: Contour Plot of the Desirability of Responses for Different Breakfast Meal Formulations

Figure 18: 3D Plot of the Desirability of Responses for Different Breakfast Meal Formulations

Table 5: Predicted and Experimental Mean Values of the Properties of the Optimal Formulation for the Production of Breakfast Meal from Whole-Wheat, Acha and Mushroom Flours

Response	Predicted Mean	Experimental Run 3	Percent deviation (%)
Protein (%)	17.75	15.16	14.59
Fibre (%)	1.04	0.96	7.69
Ca (mg/100g)	7.53	8.00	-6.24
K (mg/100g)	8.02	7.50	6.48
SWC (%)	626.75	641.49	-2.35
WAC (%)	483.58	446.47	7.67
Carr index	42.97	45.12	-5.00
Peak viscosity (RVU)	891.78	946.00	-6.08
TPC (mgGAE/g)	0.46	0.37	19.57
DPPH (%)	54.74	54.62	0.22
AGIA (%)	31.36	32.20	-2.68
AAIA (%)	48.07	53.01	-10.28

Key: Ca: Calcium; K: Potassium; SWC: Swelling capacity; WAC: Water absorption capacity; TPC: Total phenolic content; DPPH: 1, 1-diphenylpicrylhydrazine radical scavenging activity; AAIA and AGIA: α-amylase and α-glucosidase inhibitory activities.

CONCLUSION

Optimization of formulation for the production of enriched breakfast meal was successfully achieved by employing the use of I-Optimal mixture design. The increasing addition of mushroom flour to the mix improved the protein, TPC, DPPH, AAIA, AGIA and the mineral contents while wheat and acha significantly affected the functional and pasting properties of the breakfast meal positively. The selected optimum mixture for the formulation of an enriched breakfast meal based on 80.82% desirability plots was 67.90% whole-wheat flour, 22.42% acha flour and 9.68% mushroom flour while the actual optimum experimental run occurred in run 3 (65.63% wheat, 23.13% acha and 11.3% mushroom flours) that correlated closely to the run predicted by desirability plots.

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